

IMPACT OF ADVERTISEMENT ON CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR

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Abstract : Advertisement play a major role in the business Advertising has gone through many phases. The first era was production-oriented. Here mass production was seen as a means to selling products by pumping in huge volumes into the market place. As a result demand exceeded supply; hence there was no need to advertise products (Holt, D,1983). They sold themselves. To better approach the problem of selling companies tried many techniques. These techniques combined with the support activities of marketing can be called as advertising. Advertising has been considered important since the time when trade started, then was the time for advertising by mouth, now we have different media platforms for the same purpose. But still the traditional word of mouth holds the best appeal in respect to all advertising platforms.

IndexTerms- Objectives of advertisement, importance of advertisement, Types of advertisement

I. INTRODUCTION

Advertising used properly is a major tool in the hands of marketing managers which helps enable them to sell products, services and ideas. The idea is to sell products to the consumers. This has been proved by the fact that companies are investing a lot of time and resources into developing ad campaigns for their products

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However with the passing of time and due to rising competition, surplus goods were available. As a result of this companies were required to sell their products using a sales oriented mechanism. This typically involved pitching in their products, highlighting their USP's, so as to convince customers to buy their products rather than their competitors. As a result products became de linked to the volumes in which they were being produce (Belk, Russell.1974).

To better approach the problem of selling companies tried many techniques. These techniques combined with the support activities of marketing can be called as advertising. Advertising has been considered important since the time when trade started, then was the time for advertising by mouth, now we have different media platforms for the same purpose. But still the traditional word of mouth holds the best appeal in respect to all advertising platforms.

In its initial phases advertising was limited in both time and space. Broadcast commercials are generally 10 to 60 seconds in length. Print ads are generally no larger than two pages, and often much smaller. Advertising therefore needed to do its job in an effective manner. Its primary tasks were to capture the consumer's attention, identify itself as being aimed at meeting the needs of that consumer, identifying the product, and delivering the selling message.

II Objectives of Advertisement

1. Brand building:

Advertising helps in the establishment and promotion of a brand in the existing market. It also aids in the creation of new market for the brand. With the help of audio-visual advertisements, you can also reminding and reinforce the brand message into your target customers' mind.

2. Creation of demand:

One of the main objectives of advertising is that it persuades the customers to buy and use a particular product. Hence, advertising also contributes in creating brand awareness and demand. Also, advertising is the best option for promotion when it comes to launch of a new product or service. Effective and convincing advertisements do not only help establish a brand identity but also persuade competitor brand's customers to switch to a new brand.

3. Informing Customers about a Product, Company or Service:

Advertising is also a strong medium of communicating about product, company or service. Companies can tell about features, qualities or unique characteristics of their product or service in the advertisement.

4. Promoting a Particular Feature:

Specific objectives of companies can also be fulfilled with the help of advertising. Building up more positive customer attitudes, beating negative promotion, extending customer base, creating comparison in customer's mind and various other particular objectives can be attained by making a specific advertisement for the same.

5. Achieve sales and profit goals:

Advertisements create awareness about a brand and help in increasing the demand for a product or service. The increased demands results in increased sales and so, profit goals of a company are attained with the help of advertizing

III Importance of Advertising

2. Product Launch

The foremost aim of advertising is promotion. Hence, advertising is essential, especially for a new product that has to be launched in the market. Advertising helps convey the information regarding launch of the new product.

2. Retain the existing customers:

It is essential that customers keep following, buying and using your brand. And this is where advertising helps companies again! It keeps on reminding the customers about the brand and so, helps in retaining the customers and increasing the sales.

3. Brand Promotion:

Promotion is quintessential if any brand wants to stay in the market. This goal is achieved with the help of advertising which promotes a product, company or service. When a brand gets established with the help of advertising, it becomes a promise of quality and the customers start expecting from a brand. Thereafter, the stage arises where advertising starts acting as a reminder. It reminds and convinces customers that their chosen brand is still there.

4. Educates people:

Advertising is not only about promotion! It also educates people and makes the society aware about various issues. Many social issues like female foeticide, child labor, child abuse, etc., are also raised through sensible advertisements. Thus, advertising also helps in educating people and spreading awareness.

5. Comparison:

Advertising also provides the opportunity of comparing various products to the customers. Based on features, qualities or specifications described through advertising, customers can take their pick on the available products.

Statement of the Problem:

Advertisement became the important tool in the business world without advertisement the business people can't market their product to their customer. But some small scale business thought the some media of advertisement is very expensive which create more demand for their product.

Objectives of the study:

1. To examine the media of advertisement which influence the consumer to buy the product
2. To determine whether the advertisement influence the buying behavior of the consumer.

IV Review of Literature:

1. Impact of advertisement on buying behavior of the consumer: Study of cosmetics industry in Karachi city – Samar Fatima – In this study the objectives was to identify the impact of the advertisement on consumer awareness and to identify the role of advertisement on building consumer perception and findings of the study was awareness and perception are the two main drivers which force the customer to buy the particular product.

2. Hafiz Muhammad Arsad (2014) – In this study the objectives was to understand the context of effective advertising and its influence on consumer buying behavior and the findings of the study was effective advertising is the major source to generate Sensations in consumers which motivate them to buy advertising mobile phone products.

V Analysis and Interpretation:

Table – 01
Media of advertisement influencing consumer buying behavior

S.No.	Particular	No. of Respondents
1	Newspaper	50
2	Television	30
3	Radio	20
4	Internet	100
	Total	200

Source: Primary data

Interpretation:

From the above table it is indentify that 100 respondents says that internet is media which influence consumer buying behavior, 50 of the says that newspaper influence consumer buying behavior, 30 and 20 of the says that television and radio influence the consumer buying behavior

Chart – 01
Media of advertisement influencing consumer buying behavior

Table – 02
Importance given in the advertisement

S.No.	Particular	No. of Respondents
1	Benefits of the product	10
2	Brand name	55
3	Company name	15
4	Product features	120
	Total	200

Source: Primary data**Interpretation:**

From the above table it determine that 120 respondents says the advertisement should give more importance to product features, 55 of the respondents says that advertisement should give more importance to brand name, 15 and 10 of the respondents says that the advertisement should give importance to company name and benefit of the product.

Chart – 02**Importance given in the advertisement****Findings**

1. 100 respondents say that internet is the media of advertisement which influence the consumer buying behavior.
2. 120 respondents say that advertisement should give more importance to product.

Suggestion:

The advertisement should be give clear picture of the product and should attract the customer effectively and also the advertisement should give attractive manner

VII CONCLUSION

The historical period the consumer does not know about all the product but now days the consumer can easily identify the branded product and also they can easily buy the product. Previously the consumer has to spend more time in purchasing the product but now days the consumer spend less time because they can easily identify the product area, price and quality.

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